

ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION WITH THE HELP OF GOOGLE CLASSROOM

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Abstract. *This article discusses Google Classroom and how to create a course, add assignments, what didactic and electronic resources to use, and what aspects should be given importance when organizing independent education effectively. Also in the article, the integration of programs Google Classroom and Kahoot!, and examples of how to use such level of questions in the application of such integration in mathematics are discussed.*

Keywords: *independent education, Google Classroom, assignment, account, Kahoot!, integration, electronic supply, course, test.*

Introduction.

Google Classroom is a free online platform provided by Google, which is designed to simplify the organization and management of the educational process. That is, Google Classroom is a means of communication between teachers and students within a subject (or topic). Google Classroom offers a wide range of opportunities to organize the educational process. Using the platform, a teacher can create a course within a subject, add students to this course, post information about the course, create various assignments, evaluate students, and return the graded assignments to students. With Google Classroom, you can organize various individual and collective educational activities. The use of this platform helps to update educational content, expand pedagogical methods, introduce differentiated teaching technology, and organize distance education.

The modern education system directs students not only to acquire theoretical knowledge, but also to develop practical skills. Independent education is one of the important parts of this process, which aims to acquire knowledge and have the opportunity for personal development of oneself using resources independently. To achieve these goals, the Google Classroom platform is one of the convenient and effective tools that serve to create effective interaction between the teacher and the student. In this article, we sought answers to the question of how to organize independent education using Google Classroom.

Literature analysis. Currently, no studies have been conducted on the use of the Google Classroom platform in organizing independent education in Uzbekistan. However, G. H. Torayeva developed methodical recommendations for working in Google Classroom [5]. Researchers G.S. Turdiyeva and D.H. Fayziyeva conducted their scientific work on the use of Hot Potatoes and Ispring programs to create independent educational tasks [4].

In her work, D.M. Makhmudova conducted research on the development of independent creative activity of students based on the teaching of problematic mathematical tasks, the methodology of teaching problematic mathematical tasks using mathematical software packages such as MatLab, MathCad, Maple, Mathematica [1].

In his research work, S.I. Kulmamatov developed recommendations on the methodology of using computer technologies in organizing independent education, organizing independent

educational activities through electronic textbooks, and organizing independent educational activities of students using the possibilities of computer programs [3].

In the scientific works, M. U. Kochkarov considered such issues as the role and importance of the project of the educational process in independent education, the formation of the student's independent education skills through design teaching of "Higher Mathematics" [2].

Methodology. First of all, in order to organize work in Google Classroom, the user must have a Google Account. To create a course in Google Classroom, a user with an account must log in to the account through a browser and select the account after typing the name of the official website classroom.google.com in the address bar of the browser. After that, the Classroom page will open. If the user has not yet created a course or joined any courses, a screen like the one in Figure 1 will appear.

Figure 1

Figure 2

The user creates a new course by clicking on the + icon on the right side of the screen and clicking the command "Create Course" (Figure 2).

Enter the name of the course and fill in the relevant lines in the window "Создать курс". Click the button "Создать" and a new course will be created. The created course opens in a virtual audience. Each course will receive an automatic code, and course participants can join the course via the link or with this code.

Students can be attached to the course by clicking on the icon "Пригласить учащихся". That is, the e-mail addresses of the participants are written in the created line, and the course code is sent to their e-mails.

Figure 3

Figure 4

When organizing student independent learning activities in Google Classroom, the teacher adds students to the course and posts materials for students to learn independently. All kinds of files can be placed in Google Classroom as lecture and practical training materials. That is, text

documents (doc, docx), presentations (ppt, pptx), tables and calculations (xls, xlsx), image and graphic files (jpeg, png, svg, gif), audio and video files (mp3, wav, mp4, avi), archived files (zip, rar), links (URL), etc. Content can be posted from Google Drive, by linking to a web address, by uploading an existing file on your computer, and by linking to a YouTube URL.

To do this, click on the inscription “Обратитесь к курсу” in the section “Лента”, enter

the explanatory text in the resulting field and attach the materials.

by clicking on these symbols, materials from Google Drive, YouTube, files on the computer and the Internet are added, and by clicking on the icon “Опубликовать”, the data is saved.

Each student will be notified by e-mail about the placement of this information. Students who are engaged in independent educational activities will learn this information independently and if they have any questions about the course, they will send it to the comments section. Students can use this information online or download it and use it again and again whenever they want.

Analysis and results. In order to actively involve students in the independent learning process, develop their independent learning skills and monitor their mastery, it is possible to create various assignments in Google Classroom.

To create assignments in Classroom, select the section “Задания” from the menu bar of the course (Fig. 5).

Figure 5

After entering the section, click the button "Create" and select the type of task you want to create. Assignments can be added from the Google Drive cloud drive, with a URL as a link to the Internet resource. After selecting “Создать задание” from the list, a new window will appear for entering the parameters of the task (Fig. 6).

The items in the window are filled in, the required file type is attached, and the calendar on the right side of the window is adjusted. The grade of the assignment, the deadline for the assignment, the topic are entered and the button "Создать задание" is clicked. The teacher can change the assessment at his discretion.

Figure 6

When creating a course from Google Classroom, the teacher must strictly follow the following rules.

1. In the course, students should set specific goals aimed at developing independent work skills, i.e., set the educational goal of each assignment;
2. Teacher must provide adequate resources for independent activities.
3. Preparation of interactive assignments, i.e., students should create assignments based on written works, post problematic issues for students to express their opinions.
4. It should create an opportunity for self-evaluation.
5. The teacher should evaluate the work of each student individually, give them recommendations, and organize regular Google Meet sessions to ask their questions.

6. A deadline should be set for independent work to be completed on time.

Through these methods, students feel responsible, develop independent work skills, and increase self-management potential.

Questions (5) **Show answers**

1 - Quiz Muavr formulasi berilgan javobni belgilang	
<input type="checkbox"/> $z^n = r(x + iy)$	✗
<input type="checkbox"/> $z^n = r^n(\cos \varphi + i \sin \varphi)$	✗
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> $z^n = r^n(\cos n\varphi + i \sin n\varphi)$	✓
<input type="checkbox"/> $e^{i\psi} = \cos \varphi + i \sin \varphi$	✗
2 - True or false Kompleks sonlarni tekislikda tasvirlaganda y o'qi mavhum o'q deb olinadi	
3 - Quiz Trigonometrik ko'rinishdagi ikki kompleks sonning nisbati uchun qaysi ifoda to'g'ri	
4 - True or false Kompleks sondan ildiz chiqarish uchun Muavr formulasidan foydalaniladi	
5 - Quiz Kompleks sonlarni ko'paytirish qanday xossalarga ega?	
<input type="checkbox"/> Assosativlik va distributivlik	✗
<input type="checkbox"/> to'g'ri javob yo'q	✗
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Assosativlik va kommutativlik	✓
<input type="checkbox"/> Komutativlik va distributivlik	✗
3 - Quiz Qaysi biri soha	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1-chizma	✓
<input type="checkbox"/> 2-chizma	✗

Figure 7.

Modern electronic tools such as Google Drive, Google Meet, Google Docs, Google Slides and Google Chat give the teacher the opportunity to effectively organize an independent educational process on the Google Classroom platform and form its didactic support. With the help of these tools, educational materials are created, stored, shared, and students' educational activities are monitored.

Google Drive is a cloud-based storage system that allows teachers to centrally store, share, and manage student work.

Google Meet is a platform for remote communication, which allows teachers to conduct video lessons or communicate with students in real time.

Google Docs is a tool that allows students to create, edit, and share documents, fostering collaboration between teachers and students.

Google Slides is a tool for creating and presenting presentations, which allows the student to make the educational process more effective through visual materials.

Google Chat is a text communication tool that allows the teacher to quickly communicate with his students and give quick answers to questions that arise during the study.

Kahoot! is an online platform that allows you to create interactive quizzes, games and tests.

In addition, the game can be played in real time or at a time convenient for students. The game will automatically form a list of winners based on speed and correct answers.

First of all, in the program Kahoot!, there is a need to create questions about the course. Theoretical questions that do not require a lot of time, examples that can be solved quickly, as well as formulas and drawings can be used to create independent work questions on mathematics (Fig. 7).

After creating questions in the program, it is possible to place them directly in the assignment section of Google Classroom. Assignments are assigned due dates, and students receive an email notification that the assignment has been uploaded (Figures 8-9-10). Everyone participates in the game with their name and can see their points. They can see the overall result after the deadline through this link. (Figure 11).

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11.

Conclusion. The use of such integrations in independent education increases students' interest in independent education and the ability to use electronic software.

Further study of the capabilities of the Google Classroom platform, its adaptation to the educational process, and the introduction of best practices serve to increase the quality and efficiency of education.

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